

STORAGE RESEARCH INFRASTRUCTURE ECO-SYSTEM

3rd TNA Call Documentation – User

USER REPORT (WITH SATISFACTION SURVEY): USER (S)

General information about the project	
Project title (as used in application)	Metallic wools for enhancing heat transfer in phase change materials
Project acronym (max 15 characters)	MEWTES
StoRIES TNA RI(s) accessed	GREiA research group at the Universitat de Lleida
Keywords (up to ten, free text)	'Thermal energy storage', 'metallic wool', 'experimental measurements', 'phase change material', 'composite'.
Arrival date (in town where RI located)	22/11/2023
Departure date (from town where RI located)	16/12/2023
Starting date of access (first day at RI)	22/11/2023
Finishing date of access (last day at RI)	15/12/2023
Number of days not using the RI (during the above period)	9
Reason for not using RI those days (describe)	Weekends and holidays
Number of days using the RI	15
Number of users granted access (group size)	1
Comments	
Access Summary Report - work performed and initial results	
Brief description of the objectives of your project (up to 200 words)	
<p>The proposed work aimed to investigate the impact of metallic wool on the thermal behavior of phase change material (PCM) in a lab-scale shell and tube heat exchanger prototype. The study focuses on enhancing the heat transfer efficiency of PCMs using such an easily implementable solution in already built heat exchangers. The shell and tube heat exchanger has been filled with copper wool sheets placed in the radial direction of the tubes and with n-octadecane as a phase change material. Temperature sensors are strategically placed at different locations within the PCM and at the inlet and outlet sections of the heat transfer fluid (HTF) to evaluate the thermal performance of the metallic wool-PCM composite during charging and discharging cycles. The thermal behavior of the above-described case has been compared against the baseline case, i.e. solely PCM. The research aimed to assess the impact of the copper wool configuration on the heat</p>	

transfer efficiency in the specific case under study.

Activities performed (up to 600 words)

The research involved an investigation of thermal energy storage (TES) utilizing copper wool sheets as heat transfer enhancers and by comparing them to the baseline case containing solely PCM. The TES tank, designed in a shell-and-tube heat exchanger configuration, had a volumetric capacity of 3 L. The charging and discharging characteristics of this tailor-made TES tank were examined using an in-house experimental setup available at the GREiA laboratories (the RI provider). This set-up comprises a condensing unit, a buffer tank with two built-in heaters, water pumps, a flow meter, and the TES tank under study. Copper pipes with a diameter of 12.7 mm interconnected the components hydraulically, with polyurethane insulation to minimize heat loss. The TES tank was loaded with 2.4 kg of mass of n-octadecane for the two configurations tested. The heat transfer fluid (HTF) chosen was water, considering the operating temperature range between 15 ± 1 °C and 45 ± 1 °C.

The 200-L capacity buffer tank adjusted the HTF temperature using the built-in heaters and the condensing unit, while the water pump ensured a constant flow rate of HTF between the buffer tank and the TES tank. Temperature measurements were obtained using PT-100 thermocouples with an accuracy of ± 0.3 °C at the inlet and outlet sections of the TES tank for the HTF and at ten different locations within the tank for the PCM. These thermocouples were integrated into a data acquisition system, and an application developed in InduSoft Web Studio controlled the setup components.

Baseline tests were conducted with solely PCM, and the results were compared with tests where the shell and tube tank was completely filled with copper wool sheets positioned perpendicular to the axial direction of the tubes, along with PCM.

To obtain the charging process, the experimental procedure involved:

- Lowering the PCM temperature below 15 ± 1 °C before each charging cycle using cold water from the buffer tank, cooled by the condensing unit.
- The buffer tank was then heated to 46 ± 1 °C using built-in heaters.
- Subsequently, hot water was pumped through the tube side of the TES tank at 3 L/min to charge the PCM, thus obtaining the phase transition.

For the discharging cycle, an analogous procedure was exploited to obtain the thermal discharge of the PCM, by involving the cool down of the PCM from 45 ± 1 °C to 15 ± 1 °C.

The charging and discharging cycles were repeated three times for uncertainty analysis.

Scientific results (up to 800 words)

The main scientific result of the project is the assessment of the impact of the copper wool sheets on the heat transfer efficiency during the charging and discharging processes of the TES tank under study. Baseline tests were conducted with PCM, and the results were compared with the case where the TES tank was completely filled with copper wool sheets placed perpendicularly to the axial direction of the tubes, along with PCM.

The charging process was obtained by means of the flowing of the HTF within the tubes of the TES tank with a mass flow rate of 3 L/min and a temperature of 45 ± 1 °C, while in the discharging process the temperature of the HTF was 15 ± 1 °C.

The peak temperature of n-octadecane during melting is reported at 28.07 °C, while it is at 26.60 °C for the solidification, thus denoting a small degree of subcooling of the material.

The comparison between the two configurations was obtained by considering the ten

thermocouples that have been placed at different locations within the TES tank. An average of the temperatures detected by the thermocouples has been considered as a function of the discharging and charging periods tested for both configurations.

The figure of merit chosen for the comparison between the configurations was the time needed to reach the target temperature of 45°C (15°C) within the TES tank during the charging (discharging) process.

Three tests for the discharging and charging processes for each configuration have been performed to perform an uncertainty analysis.

During the charging process, the time needed to reach the target temperature of 40 °C was 35 minutes for the baseline case, while for the PCM+copper wool was 31.8 minutes (9.35% decrease in the charging time).

For the discharging process, the time needed to reach 20°C decreased from 190.6 minutes (solely PCM) to 39.9 minutes (composite), thus reaching an outstanding decrease of 79%. More in detail, a decrease in the discharging time per unit mass of copper wool of 197 minutes/kg was obtained with the tested copper wool configuration.

The results reported for the composite, have been obtained with 0.765 kg of wool, thus resulting in 31.8 % in weight with respect to the PCM, but solely to 2.93% in volume, thanks to the remarkable difference in density between the PCM (865 kg/m³ solid and 785 kg/m³ liquid) and the copper fibres (8960 kg/m³). Therefore, a negligible increase in volume was present in the configuration with copper wools, thus allowing all the experiments to be performed with the same PCM mass within the TES tank.

Interpretation of the results (up to 400 words)

The figure of merit considered, i.e. the time needed to reach a target temperature during the charging and discharging processes, allowed a comparison of the behaviour of the two configurations considered, thus obtaining the assessment of the impact of the copper wool sheets on the heat transfer within the already designed TES tank.

Two different impacts of the copper wool have been obtained for the charging and the discharging processes, with an outstanding result in the discharging one.

This different impact is due to the distinct nature of the two phenomena. During the charging process, in fact, the copper wool increases the heat conduction within the PCM but, at the same time, it limits the movement of the liquid phase of the PCM, thus hindering the natural convection. On the other hand, the discharging phenomenon is dominated by heat conduction, so the addition of the wool does not present such a drawback.

Importantly, in PCM-based tanks, the discharging period is usually the bottleneck for several practical applications, as it is usually remarkably longer than the charging one, as was evident in the performed experiment for the baseline case.

Moreover, the here presented results have been obtained by adding a negligible volume fraction of the copper wool within the tank, thus allowing the same mass of PCM of the baseline case. In applications where the weight of the component is not relevant, therefore, the presented solution can be considered as an easily implementable heat transfer enhancer in already built TES tanks based on PCM.

The wool configuration tested in this project consisted of adding the sheets of copper wool perpendicularly to the tubes up to the complete filling of the TES tank. Therefore, it should represent the maximum limit in the decrease of discharging times to reach the specified target temperature. Still, optimized configurations of the wool within the TES tank may reach a similar decrease with a lower amount of wool, thus impacting the whole cost of the components.

Main achievements during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)
<p>The project's primary achievement lies in a comprehensive assessment of the impact of copper wool sheets on heat transfer efficiency within a TES tank utilizing PCM. Through baseline tests with PCM and comparative experiments incorporating copper wool sheets, the study focused on charging and discharging processes. The chosen figure of merit, representing the time required to reach target temperatures, facilitated a comprehensive comparison.</p> <p>The findings revealed distinct impacts during charging and discharging. While copper wool enhanced heat conduction, during charging it constrained natural convection due to the reduced movement of the liquid PCM. Conversely, in the discharging phase dominated by heat conduction, the addition of copper wool presented no drawbacks, showcasing its outstanding potential as a heat transfer enhancer. Significantly, as discharging periods often pose practical bottlenecks, the copper wool configuration demonstrated a remarkable reduction in discharging times, crucial for several real-world applications.</p> <p>Moreover, the project demonstrated the feasibility of integrating copper wool as a heat transfer enhancer without the need to diminish the mass of PCM for a constant volume, making it particularly attractive for applications where component weight is not a constraint. The configured wool placement, though tested at maximum packing density, hinted at potential optimization opportunities, suggesting that even more efficient configurations might be achievable with reduced wool amounts, impacting component costs positively. In essence, the study provides valuable insights for implementing practical and cost-effective heat transfer enhancements in existing TES tanks based on PCM technology.</p>
Difficulties during the TNA related work (up to 250 words)
The whole equipment was accessible during the TNA period.
Intended publications
<p>A journal paper regarding the experiments carried out in the context of the StoRIES project is planned, by comparing numerical simulations and experimental measurements of the charging and discharging processes of both the baseline case (solely PCM) and the PCM+wool composite. The target journal has still not been defined.</p> <p>Moreover, the results obtained by these experimental measurements are planned to be presented at the 9th European Thermal Sciences Conference (EUROTHERM 2024).</p>
Data management
The data of the experiments performed have been acquired by means of the acquisition data present in the experimental setup of the hosting group. They are currently stored within the server of the hosting Group (RI provider) and by the user.
Conclusions / additional comments

Did you complete the EC user questionnaire available at https://ec.europa.eu/eusurvey/runner/RIsurveyUSERS ? (necessary)					
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No					
Feedback – HSE, Ethics and Satisfaction					
Please rate on a scale from 1 (excellent) to 5 (poor). Feel free to provide additional comments					
Practical information on how to apply for Transnational Access and the overall application process	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Information provided, once your project was accepted, on how to proceed	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
Support received at the site(s) regarding technical/scientific matters and logistics	Have you got sufficient support from the RI staff during the project? If not, please, specify the problems. <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Yes <input type="checkbox"/> No				
RI extension / upgrades required	In your opinion, is the RI needed to be upgraded? If yes, please give an explanation. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Problems with local regulations	Have you had any problems with regulations of the visited RI owner (HSE, lab working hours, etc.)? If yes, please, specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Health and safety issues	Did you encounter any health or safety issue during your research? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to the environment, to animals or plants? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				

Environment & Ethics	Did your research deal with endangered fauna and/or flora and/or protected areas? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Environment & Ethics	Did your research involve the use of elements that may cause harm to humans, including research staff? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Environment & Ethics – Dual use	Does your research have the potential for military applications? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Environment & Ethics – Misuse	Does your research have the potential for malevolent /criminal/terrorist abuse? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Environmental issues	Were any potentially dangerous substances (materials / gases etc.) released into the environment (atmosphere, water, or land)? Please provide details. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Ethics issues	Are there any other ethics issues that should be taken into consideration? Please specify <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No										
Overall impression of communication and interaction after finishing your TNA related work	<table border="1"> <thead> <tr> <th>1 (excellent)</th> <th>2</th> <th>3 (neutral)</th> <th>4</th> <th>5 (poor)</th> </tr> </thead> <tbody> <tr> <td style="text-align: center;"><input checked="" type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> <td style="text-align: center;"><input type="checkbox"/></td> </tr> </tbody> </table>	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>
1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)							
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Suggestions for facilities not included in StoRIES which you would use for your research											
Suggestions how StoRIES can improve future TNA programme, how to make the TNA more impactful on the energy storage technologies and how to enable the achievement of high TRL levels.											
Feedback – Pro-active Innovation Support											

Awareness	Did you know about the pro-active innovation support of StoRIES. <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Personal experience	Have you taken advantage of or benefited from the pro-active innovation support? <input type="checkbox"/> Yes <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> No				
Information/service provided by the pro-active innovation support?	1 (excellent)	2	3 (neutral)	4	5 (poor)
	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>	<input type="checkbox"/>

I declare that the above provided information and especially that information on the number of days visited the RI is correct.